

EMERGENCE AND STUDY OF UZBEK ONOMASTICS

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Abstract: This article discusses the field of "Onomastics" (Famous nouns), which is one of the branches of modern linguistics today, and its theoretical foundations, units, the concept of onomastic scale, and considerations related to its research.

Key words: onomastics, toponyms, urbanonym, godonym, anthroponyms, cosmonymics, zoonyms, ornithonyms, lexical basis, onomastic unity, onomastic scope.

Абстракт: В данной статье рассматривается область "Ономастика" (существительные), которая сегодня является одной из отраслей современного языкознания, а также ее теоретические основы, единицы, понятие ономастической шкалы и соображения, связанные с ее исследованием.

Ключевые слова: ономастика, топонимы, урбаноним, годоним, антропонимы, космонимика, зоонимы, орнитонимы, лексическая основа, ономастическая единица, ономастическая сфера.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda zamonaviy tilshunoslik sohalaridan biri bo'lgan "Onomastika" sohasi, uning nazariy asoslari, birliklari, onomastik ko'lam tushunchasi va uning tadqiqiga oid mulohazalar keltirilgan. Bu soha nomlar, ularning vazifalari, rivojlanishi, paydo bo'lish tarixini geografik, tarixiy, sotsiologik, filosofik, etnografik va psixologik aspektida o'rganadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *onomastika, toponimlar, urbanonim, godonim, antroponimlar, kosmonimika, zoonimlar, ornitonimlar, lug'aviy asos, onomastik birlik, onomastik ko'lam.*

INTRODUCTION.

Names have long been the focus of scientists and philosophers, both in the East and in the West. The development of any science is always accompanied by the formation and improvement of the terminological system, and the formation of a new science can lead to a real terminological discovery. Onomastics is not a new science, but a collection of unique names.

Onomastics comes from the Greek *onomastike*, *onyma*, which means "the art of naming" and is the branch of linguistics that studies all proper names, the history of their origin and change, as well as the sum of all proper names. Currently, onomastics has become an independent science and has developed completely new directions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Formation processes of onomastics N.V. Related to the name Podolskaya. N.V. Podolskaya used the term onomastics for the first time in her "Dictionary of Russian Onomastic Terminology" ("Slovar russkoy onomasticheskoy terminologii") published in 1978 (first edition). This dictionary was created by the well-known linguist - the classic of Russian onomastics A.V. Edited by Superanskaya, all modern researchers of theoretical onomastics

rely on it in their work. N. V. Podolskaya in her dictionary defined the term onomastics as "the branch of linguistics that studies any famous names" [1].

In the "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" compiled by the famous French linguist J. Maruzot, "Onomastics... refers to the system of personal names of a certain language or a certain region, or the branch that studies this system. [2]" is cited.

D.E. Rosenthal and M.A. Telenkova's "Dictionary of Linguistic Terms - Reference" describes it as "Onomastics ... a branch of lexicology dedicated to the study of proper names" [3].

The term "onomastics" means "a collection of famous names" and N.V. Podolskaya herself emphasized this. Later, Russian linguistics in the "Big encyclopedic dictionary" (Bolshoy entsiklopedichesky slovar) onomastics "1) specific names and their types; 2) used as a branch of lexicology that studies names [4].

- ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

To sum up, the term onomastics is used both in the sense of "a branch of linguistics that studies names (department of lexicology)" and in the sense of "a set of specific names". However, we think that onomastics should be seen not as a branch of lexicology, but as an independent linguistic science [5].

In modern linguistics, there are the following forms of onomastics:

1. Theoretical onomastics - studies the general laws of the development and operation of onomastic systems;
2. Practical onomastics - studies issues such as naming practice, use and change of names in speech;
3. Descriptive onomastics - studies such as philological analysis and linguistic interpretation of the collected material;
4. Poetic onomastics - deals with the onomastics of artistic works;
5. Historical onomastics - studies the history of the emergence of names and the influence of different historical realities and their reflection in names;
6. Ethnic onomastics - deals with the emergence of the names of ethnic groups and their parts in connection with the history of ethnic groups, the relationship of ethnonyms with other names, the evolution of ethnonyms, etc.
7. Modern onomastics is devoted to today's onomastic processes and their research.

In Uzbekistan, onomastics has become one of the most developed fields since the second half of the last century, and a lot of work has been done in its branches. Until now, mainly toponyms, hydronyms, oronyms, anthroponyms, ethnonyms have been studied. The materials of Uzbek names (anthroponyms) were thoroughly collected, four candidate theses (E. Begmatov - 1965, G. Sattorov - 1990, S. Rahimov - 1998, R. Khudoyberganov - 2007) were defended, E. Begmatov's "Spelling of Personal Names" (1970), "Spelling of Uzbek Names" (1972), "Uzbek Names" (1991), "Meaning of Uzbek Names" (1998; 2004; 2010), "The Beauty of Names" (1994) books were published. In the research entitled "From the history of Central Asian names", the theories presented about ethnonyms-toponyms, hydronyms, oronyms, toponymic areas, toponymic map show the development of the field. Other types of famous horses were not the object of monographic studies. The development of scientific research on Uzbek onomastics led to the emergence and formation of the language of onomastic analysis today. As a result of this, in Uzbek linguistics, various directions have emerged that determine the concepts of onomastics, linguistic features of common nouns, and research methods.

After the independence of our country, our life changed dramatically, foreign economic and cultural relations entered the stage of development. As a result, many place names, streets, villages, squares, water bodies, farms, firms, trade-related shops, and private enterprises began to appear. As each object appears, it must have a name.

DISCUSSION.

The onomastic field of any language, including the Uzbek language, is a linguistic entity that is extremely complex and extensive, mutually different according to nominative-functional characteristics, and at the same time, it has a certain connection and relationship with each other.

While studying scientific information and research on onomastics, we come across such concepts as scale, micro and macro scale. Based on this definition, if we turn to Uzbek onomastics, the onomastic scope of the Uzbek language is formed by the set of all types and forms of famous nouns in this language. In his research, the well-known onomologist Ernest Begmatov divides the onomastic scope into micro (small) and macro (large) types [6].

A comprehensive study of all available types and sizes of common nouns in a given language helps to determine the scope of common nouns in that language and their onomastic scope. This problem is interpreted in onomastic studies in connection with the concept and term called "onomastic scope" ("onomasticheskoe prostranstvo") [6]. The term onomastic (toponomastic) scope, which is used to designate the entire set of onomastic names, was first introduced into the scientific debate by V.N. Toporov, and later A.V. Superanskaya used the terms "onomastic scope" and "toponymic scope" in her research [7]. The word "prostranstvo" has many meanings, it is: 1) space, space, void in philosophy; 2) in a simple sense: wide level, area, place, space; 3) represents a large latitude on the surface of the earth [8]. So, this term can also be called onomastic level, onomastic field. However, the essence of the concepts studied in the field of onomastics by E. Begmatov is: 1) what types of proper nouns exist in a certain language; 2) the limit of distribution of nouns in speech practice; 3) in general, depending on the size of the onomastic lexicon of this language, he emphasizes that the terms level and field are narrow to convey these meanings. Therefore, it is appropriate to express the word "prostranstvo" with the word "scope". The meaning of this word can be understood from the explanation given to it. "Scope - the level of spread, scope, volume, scale, development, and escalation of a business activity" [9].

A.V. Superanskaya describes the correctness and convenience of the concept of "onomastic scope" on the example of toponymic scope as follows: "This term is the location of names and named objects in space, that is, their existence separately from each other, and this is their the earth is also convenient in terms of the fact that it is outside of it" [0].

Just as the lexical wealth of the language is made up of concrete lexical units (lexemes), the onomastic scope of the language is made up of concrete proper nouns embodied in the onomastic lexicon. According to A.V. Superanskaya: "The onomastic scope is a set of nouns used to name real, imaginary and imaginary objects in a certain vernacular" [6].

E. Begmatov's book "Anthroponymics of the Uzbek language" in the classification of onomastic terms of the Uzbek language is as follows:

The onomastic macroscope is a large division after the superscope, in which the nominative units that organize and unite on the basis of certain signs of the onomastic system of the language and make up the onomastic microscope are embodied. For example, specific noun types are included in the macroscope of anthroponymy as a noun related to the human concept, in the macroscope of toponymy as the name of physical-geographical objects located on land, and in the macroscope of cosmonymy as the name of celestial (space) objects. Such large scales help to understand the size and scope of the onomastic scope of the national language in a more general way.

The macroscope of Uzbek onomastics includes anthroponymy, zoonymy, theonymy, toponymy, cosmonymy. The units included in the macroscale make up the microscale. Toponyms are one of the macroscope of the Uzbek language. They are the names of natural geographic and artificial (man-made) objects located on the land surface of the Earth. The toponym macroscope includes 11 microscopes. These are oikonym, comonym, urbanonym, agroonym, necronym, terronym, regionim, dromonym, horonym, drimonym, insulonym groups.

Large macroscales, small microscales and even smaller scales of famous noun types interact, one is created from the other, one creates and complements the other.

- CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

Of course, the main criterion in defining onomastic scopes is the nominative-functional feature of the proper noun, but this feature, the need, is the basis for the creation of concrete onomastic units. These units are one of the word types - a specific linguistic material, a lexical unit as a noun. Lexical unity is the wealth of language, a phenomenon belonging to it.

We can say that the onomastic scope of the Uzbek language is an extremely complex and extensive concept. One of the urgent problems of Uzbek nomenclology is to carefully collect the material of nouns belonging to all macro-scale, micro-scale and scales of the Uzbek language, to study their nominative, motivational, and functional properties. Such a large-scale study is not only theoretical, but also of great practical importance for the field of onomastics. Because the results of such a scientific work demonstrate the extremely complex and rich vocabulary of our language, it closely helps to carry out the work of naming natural and geographical objects on a scientific basis, and the deep roots of the history, culture, spirituality and language of the Uzbek people. serves as a rich source of material for our deeper understanding..

References:

1. Podolskaya N. V. Dictionary of Russian onomastic terms. 2-e izd., pererab. i dop. M., 1988. 96-95
2. Maruzo J. Dictionary of linguistic terms. M., 1960.
3. Rosenthal D. E., Telenkova M. A. Slovar-spravochnik lingvisticheskikh terminov: Posobie dlya uchitelya. 2-e izd., ispr. i dop. M., 1985.
4. Big encyclopedic dictionary. M.; SPb., 2000. (Anthroponymy, Toponymy).
5. Matveev A. K. Name of Apology // Vopr. onomastic 2004. No. 1. S. 7-13.
6. Begmatov E. A. Anthroponymics of the Uzbek language / -Tashkent: Fan, 2013. -264 6.
7. Toporov V. N. Iz oblasti teoreticheskoy toponomastiki / / Voprosm yazykoznaniya.] 962. No. 6. S. 3-4; Ego eat. O paliyskoy toponomastike / / Toponymy Vostoka. Issledovaniya i material M., 1969.
8. Russian-Uzbek dictionary. Two volumes. Volume II. Tashkent, 1984. 264 pages.
9. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Two volumes. Volume I. M., 1981. Page 414
10. Theory and methodology of onomastic research. S. 8.
11. Oblanazarovna, S. N. (2022, March). PARADIGMATIC RELATIONS OF FOLLOWING CONJUNCTIONS. In E Conference Zone (pp. 3-8).
12. Oblanazarovna, S. N. (2022). LIMITED TERMS AND THEIR SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS. INTERNAUKA, 3, 79.

